

**VUNOKLANG MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL
OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY EDUCATION**
(Faculty of Education, Modibbo Adama University, Yola)

ISSN: 2276-8114

Available online at <https://vmjste.com.ng>

**THEORETICAL AND CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK FOR IMPROVING TEACHER EDUCATION
IN TERTIARY INSTITUTIONS IN GOMBE STATE, NIGERIA**

Ali Adamu¹ and Muazu Abdul²

¹Department of Mathematics and Statistics, Federal College of Education (Technical), Gombe

²National Institute of Policy and Strategic Studies (NIPSS), Kuru, Plateau State, Nigeria

Corresponding Author: aliboderi@yahoo.com, 08027983526

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15686129>

ABSTRACT

Teacher education is a well-established area of research within the education literature from global and regional perspectives which reflects different contexts. However, studies focused on Nigeria have primarily examined the challenges faced by teachers in the educational sector. Notably, there is a discernible gap in research concerning how to improve teacher education in tertiary institutions in Gombe State in view of its importance which include; improved service delivery, increased learning retention, and enhanced understanding of issues. Utilizing a literature review approach, this paper proposes a theoretical and conceptual framework for improving teachers' education in the study area. The framework draws upon the explanatory power of two relevant and interconnected theories: the Transformative Learning Theory (TLT) and the Human Capital Theory (HCT). These theoretical lenses are employed to understand and explain the improvement process of teachers' education in the study area. This research carries significant implications for both theory and practice. It will elicit government support for policy development aimed at promoting teachers' education in Gombe state. It should positively influence heads of tertiary institutions to seriously consider and strategically plan for improving teacher education with potential to stimulate further scholarly inquiry into this crucial area within the Nigerian context.

Keywords: Teacher education, Transformative Learning Theory (TLT), Human Capital Theory (HCT), Theoretical and Conceptual Framework

INTRODUCTION

Understanding the causes and contexts that influence teacher's education is a growing area of research interest around the world (Suib, Ghazali, Halim, Ariffin, Razak, 2022; Rob, 2020). The role played by teachers in the development of the educational system of each country cannot be overstated and it is considered as an important asset. (Ambotang, & Hmid, 2021; Rodrick, 2020). This is because high-performing teachers were proven to have a significant impact on student accomplishment as well as organizational success (Hartinah et al., 2020). The Federal Ministry of Education has set a goal to raise the country's educational standards to global best practices as stated in the National Policy of Education (NPE), published in 1977 and revised in 1981, 1998 and 2004). This implies that in order to fulfill the goals of the Nigerian policy on Education, teachers who are highly devoted and perform well at work are required.

Teacher education is any form of established programmes or procedures designed to prepare teachers with the behaviour, knowledge, skills required to perform the teaching activities effectively in the class room, institution and the general public (Buabeng, Ntow, & Otami, 2020). Teacher education and education sector performance are two interrelated paths to achieving socio-economic growth and development globally. It is considered to be the foundation for quality and relevance in education at all levels (Osokoya, 2022). The advent of globalisation is one of the most transformational projects in modern society (World Bank (2024).

Teacher education has been considered very relevant for Nigeria's societal development as it serves as the foundation for quality and relevant education at all levels of the system. Recently, there is a remarkable improvement in teachers education when compared with the period prior to the country's independence, and the last decades (Osokoya, 2022). The National Policy on Education (NPE) published in 1977 and revised in 1981, 1998 and 2004 clearly articulates the importance attached to teacher education and affirms that "no education system can rise above the quality of its teachers". The Policy mentioned the following thirteen (13) teacher's education goals which include: Producing well motivated, efficient and effective, teachers that could serve at the various levels of the education system and foster the development of skills in creativity and enquiry among teachers. These qualities could help teachers to adapt into the social life of the communities and the nation in general, and elicit a sense of patriotism and national cohesion. Others include; producing teachers with the requisite knowledge and skill that would match the challenges teachers may likely encounter in real times, and become accustomed to changing circumstances. These would increase teachers' commitment to their professional calling (Oviawe, Imhangbe, Aluede, Obinya, & Oke, 2022). In addition, the Policy makes it mandatory for all teachers in Nigeria to be trained and obtained the stipulated Nigeria Certificate of Education (NCE) as the minimum qualification to qualify as a professional teacher (Osokoya, 2022).

In addition, the successive Government came up with national development plans such as the economic recovery and growth plan (E&GP) (2017-2020) and the new National Economic Plan (2021-2025) with a view to strengthening sectoral performance in the country, including the education sector (Federal Ministry of Budget, 2024). These led to significant strides in improving the education sector including the enforcement of the free and compulsory basic education law by ensuring that children within the school age are brought back to school. For example, based on the implementation of the economic recovery and growth plan, from 2017, the number of Out-of-School children was reduced by 46 per cent from 12,700,000 to 6,946,328 as at December 2020 (Abdul-jabbar, 2022). There was particular focus by Government to school-age girls and a Female Scholarship Scheme (FSS) through the introduction of improved enrolment of girls in Technical, Vocational Education and Training (TVET), and Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics (STEM) System (NEP, 2021).

Furthermore, the federal government implemented a proactive Teacher Training Plan in collaboration with State Governments, including Gombe State under which 2,288,091 professional teachers have been registered and licensed after passing qualifying examinations (Adesina, Yomi, & Aliyu, 2023). The Government also registered and trained 7,400 Teachers, Quality Assurance Evaluators, and the educational management and information system (EMIS). This was meant to boost performance and bridge the digital skills gap for officers across the different cadres of the educational sector, given the current emphasis on digital literacy (Bashari, Usman, & Kala, 2023). There was also a significant milestone in the development of a National Skills Qualifications Framework (NSQF) to stimulate and promote on a massive scale relevant skills and provide local content across all sectors of the economy (Kuroshi, 2019; Odusanmi & Unoma, 2011) and

inauguration of a Research and Innovation Steering Committee to drive massive research and innovation activities in tertiary institutions in Nigeria (NEP, 2021).

Suib, Ghazali, Halim, Ariffin, and Razak (2022) reported that previous studies/research investigated not only teachers' performance evaluations, but also a range of other variables of teacher performance, such as job satisfaction and retention in the field. Similarly, many factors influence student learning (Kampeza, 2013). However, it is increasingly clear that what teachers know and are able to do is one of the most important of all. Teachers are the ones who work directly with students, who translate and shape curricular goals and theoretical ideas into classroom practice and who shape the environment for learning. Teachers' knowledge, skills, attitudes, and dispositions have direct and serious implications on the students they teach. This implied that learning is an important investment in human capital development, the aim being to ensure conducive teaching and learning that is up to date and effective (Timperley, Wilson, Barrar, & Fung, 2007).

However, in order to better grasp the present state of job performance in educational settings, it has become necessary to conduct a thorough review of the literature and to develop a Theoretical Framework for Teacher Education and Performance in Tertiary Institutions in Gombe State. Anecdotal evidence suggested that the study area (Gombe state, Nigeria) is not fully exploiting the enormous potential of its human and material resources. This has led to decline in performance of teacher education (Adamu, 2021, 2023, 2024; Abdullahi, 2024). In addition, the education system is currently failing to provide the competencies needed by teacher education for improved performance and sustained economic growth as established by Adamu (2024), and Abduljabbar (2022). In addition, The COVID-19 Pandemic has raised awareness of the imperative to mould a resilient and educated workforce that could match the requirements of the 21st century in sectors such as such as manufacturing, agriculture, and the digital economy (World Bank, 2023). Furthermore, on the national level, Nigeria faces daunting challenges in its ability to provide quality education for all children and youth, including training well educated teachers that are knowledgeable and skillful, with the competencies required to boost education sector performance (Bebeji, 2023) This is due largely to uneven access and inadequate resources to facilitate the realisation of the educational aspirations. These challenges hitherto affect all the State Governments, particularly Gombe State (Gombe State UBEC, 2024; Gombe State Ministry of Education, 2024; Adamu, 2024). The situation in Gombe State, Nigeria has resulted in challenges such as a rapidly rising population, where 44 per cent is below the age of 15, put considerable stress on the educational sector (Gombe State Ministry of Finance, 2024). There is also uneven access and inequality (equity) across all levels of enrolment along the rural-urban regional and gender divide. In addition, Girls face additional cultural limitations in certain communities where they face exclusion from educational opportunities simply due to their gender issues (Avgitidou & Sidiropoulou, 2020). There are in-adequate infrastructural and instructional materials with deficient curriculum coupled with insufficient budget allocation to invest in the education system with particular focus to teacher education. There are other challenging including low digital literacy; a supply gap in TVET; limited provision for children with learning disabilities living in vulnerable circumstances as well as insecurity such kidnappings of schools, which led to the closure of many schools (Bebeji, 2023)

According to Rashid (2024), and corroborated by UNICEF (2023), there were 550,000 out of school children in Gombe State alone. Recently, the numbers of out of school children have risen partly due to the settlement or rehabilitation of some people from the displaced states (United Nations Education, Scientific and Cultural Organisation, 2023). Thus the number of IDPs was projected to be around 600,000. However, in the last three years, reported that in the past three or four years, Gombe state Government have been able to mop about 350,000 IDPs.

The implications of the foregoing are that past research investigated not only addressed teachers' performance evaluations, but also at a range of other variables of teacher performance, such as job satisfaction and retention in the field (Suib, Ghazali, Halim, Ariffin, & Razak, 2022). Therefore, in order to better grasp the present state of job performance in educational settings, it has become necessary to conduct a thorough review of the literature and to develop a Theoretical framework for improving Teacher education and the performance in the study area (Gombe State).

In addition, Suib, Ghazali, Halim, Ariffin, and Razak (2022) had suggested that future research should address the following challenges: Qualitative research to discover further about teachers' performance, and extend knowledge in analyzing teacher performance to achieve better quality of education for next generation. This implied knowledge gap which needs to be filled. It is against this backdrop that this paper seeks to develop a theoretical and conceptual framework for improving teacher education in Gombe state, Nigeria.

The findings of the study would be of great significance to Gombe State in its quest towards enhancing teacher education. The study would specifically be useful to policymakers, Gombe State Ministry of higher Education, all tertiary institutions, and stakeholders in educational sector of the study area (Gombe State). It will also be useful to policymakers in any efforts aimed at improving teacher education in general. The study would further add value to the existing literature on the subject matter.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Teachers' education is one of the most popular and widely studied areas in the education sector. This can be attributed to the dramatic expansion of tertiary institutions in Nigeria and increasing interest in them. However, most research in this area has been conducted in other climes. For instance, USA, UK, Singapore and reflects different contexts. For instance, Conijn, Rietdijk, Broekhof, Andre, & Schinkel (2021) presented a theoretical framework that identified eight (8) teaching strategies and three (3) school policy dimensions relevant for teachers and schools to stimulate wonder in children. Conijn et al (2021) developed multidimensional Wonder-full Education questionnaire (WEQ), and revealed two (2) primary dimensions of teaching strategies. They concluded that the new framework allow research on wonder in education to be extended from mainly theoretical work to empirical research that can also advance educational practice. However, the study did not adequately address peculiar problems associated with improving tertiary education in Nigeria as it did not indicate how such issues can be addressed in Nigerian context.

In New Zealand, Timperley, Wilson, Barrar, & Fung (2007) evaluated teacher's professional learning and development, and reaffirmed the need for teachers to address the challenges which include lack of instructional materials, poor learning facilities, in adequate infrastructure, and dedicated teachers, among others.

Some studies on improving/enhancing teacher education were conducted in South Africa, Malaysia, Tanzania, and Mozambique (For instance; Ndebele, Morongwe, Ncanywa, Matope, Ginyigazi, Chisango, Nsidwana, & Garidzirai, 2024; Nordin, Noor, Mutalib, & Sidek, 2021). However, these were mainly on the kindergarten, primary and secondary schools. In addition, many schools from different developing countries; e.g Malaysia, Indonesia, Pakistan, Korea, Turkey have started to consider reforms in their tertiary institutions with a view to addressing the demands of the 21st century (Andric, 2023; Arora; 2002). Studies have also been carried out on tertiary institutions in Nigeria with regards to teacher education within the educational sector. For instance, Adamu (2021) assessed the perception of teachers on motivational factors for enhancing teaching profession in Gombe Local Government Area of Gombe, state. Similarly, the National Universities Commission

(NUC) have reported that private tertiary institutions outnumbered the public tertiary institutions in the Nigerian educational sector (NUC, 2025).

According to Bashari, Usman, and Kala (2023), teachers in tertiary institutions possessed superior class room management skills and delivered higher levels of productivity in terms of teaching and learning when compared with teachers in private tertiary institutions in Nigeria. Bashari, Usman, and Kala (2023). concluded that most public tertiary institutions have policy on improving teachers' education. In another study, Aglazor (2017) indicated that when compared with teachers in tertiary institutions, private schools teachers have comprehensive marketing strategies and key performance indicators, which results into superior quality output, and better performance.

On their part, Jaafar, Ubale, & Maigari (2023) investigated the challenges of education and diversity in Gombe State, and disclosed that most proprietors of educational institutions failed to invest in educational equipments and strategic management practices necessary to attain high quality standards in education.

Avgitidou and Sidiropoulou (2020) investigated intervention programme in the framework of teaching practice with particular focus on deconstructing and reconstructing the beliefs of candidate teachers. Despite these arrays of studies, there exists a dearth of research on improving teachers' education in the study area, as no study was found to have provided a theoretical and conceptual framework for improving teacher education in tertiary institutions in the study area.

In addition, it is also not known the limit to which models/frameworks developed for improving teachers education in other climes such as the USA, UK, and Japan among others were adopted/adapted to improve teacher education as lamented by Abduljabbar (2022) in his research on teacher education and national development in Nigeria.

Furthermore, improving teachers education could also offer teachers in tertiary institutions opportunities to acquire a lot of valuable experience and confidence through teaching practice and research activities and obtain necessary knowledge and know-how in the following aspects: Financial risk, cost factor differences due to variations that may arise between countries; taxation, customs, administrative conditions, unionisation, policies of various institutions requiring regular monitoring and review; culture, climate, people & traditional differences; and distance communication & coordination affecting management decisions on education (Adesina, Yomi, & Aliyu, 2023).

This study attempts to fill these gaps in knowledge by exploring theoretical and conceptual framework for improving teachers' education in the study area (Gombe state, Nigeria). It is hoped that the findings from this study will help heads of tertiary institutions in the study area to address the some of the challenges associated with the decline in educational standards that will yield positive results for greater educational attainment.

PURPOSE OF THE STUDY

The purpose of the study is to explore and develop a theoretical and conceptual framework for improving teachers' education in tertiary institutions in Gombe state, Nigeria with a view to achieving excellent performance in tertiary education in the study area.

RESEARCH QUESTION(S)

The study seeks to answer the following questions: What recommendations can be proffered to enhance teachers' education in order to improve achieve excellent performance in tertiary education in the study area (Gombe State?)

HYPOTHESIS

The study is guided by the following hypothesis: There exists theoretical/conceptual framework for improving teachers' education in Gombe state, Nigeria.

LITERATURE REVIEW

There are many variables that impact the teacher's job performance. Some scholars focused on a single variable: For instance administration and management (Ambotang & Hamid, 2021). Similarly, some scholars investigated multiple variables. Some scholars in Malaysia, have studied leadership as a major factor that can impact on teachers (Aglazor, 2017; Nordin, Noor, Mutalib, & Sidek, 2021). For instance, Naz and Rashid (2021) focused on teacher's motivation. Other researchers focused on teacher's self-efficacy. However, many others for instance; Thien et al (2021), Jalapang and Raman (2020), Musa et al (2020), and Ndebele, Morongwe, Ncanywa, Matope, Ginyigazi, Chisango, Nsidwana, and Garidzirai (2024) focused on teacher's commitment. In the same vein, some authors such as Abdullah et al (2020), Abas and Basri (2019) focused on teacher's development, while Ismail et al (2020) and Ismail et al (2018) emphasized on teacher's competency. The implication is that these recent studies' propensity to include the leadership of institutions (e.g principals/heads masters) demonstrates government's increasing interest and efforts to support measures aimed at enhancing teachers' job performance considering that there are several aspects that influence teacher performance, in addition to institution's leadership.

According to Arora (2002), teacher education refers to research and training of persons to teach from pre-primary to higher education level. In other words, it is a programme designed towards the development of teacher proficiency and competence, which in turn enable and empower the teacher to meet the requirements of the profession and face the challenges that may arise. On the other hand, Oyekan (2000) described teacher education as the leveraging of professional education and specialised training for some period of time for the developing individuals who intend to train and mentor the young ones to become patriotic, responsible and productive citizens. This is informed by the fact that teaching is an all-purpose profession, which stimulates the development of mental, physical and emotional powers of students.

Rob (2020) views performance as the achievement of quantified objectives. However, performance is an important and serious issue that needs to be achieved. High-performance happens due to appropriate behaviour and the proper use of acquired knowledge, skills and competencies. Performance management involves examining how results are obtained, which in turn provides the information necessary to consider what needs to be done to improve those results. On the other, Brumbrach (1988) considered performance in two (2) ways: behaviours and results. Brumbrach stressed that behaviour emanates from the performace and transforms performance from abstraction to action. Behaviour is also considered as a result or outcome in its own right; an outcome of a mental and physical effort, exerted on tasks which can be judged and is different from results. This paper considered performance as a task that leads to managing a specified process in both behavioural and result oriented terms. Therefore, this concept will be adopted for this paper.

Conijn, Rietdijk, Broekhof, Andre, & Schinkel (2022) presented a theoretical framework that identify eight (8) teaching strategies and three (3) school policy dimensions relevant to teachers and schools designed to stimulate wonder in children. Conijn et al (2022) identified two (2) primary dimensions of teaching strategies for stimulating wonder. Conijn et al (2022) concluded that the developed framework and questionnaire allowed research regarding wonder in education to be extended from mainly theoretical work to empirical research that can also advance educational practice. The outcome is consistent with the three principles of learning identified by Timperley, Wilson, Barrar, and Fung (2007) as followed:

- People come to learning with preconceptions about how the world works. If their initial understanding is not engaged, they may fail to grasp the new concepts and information that are taught or may learn them superficially and revert to their preconceptions in real situations.

Timperley, Wilson, Barrar, and Fung (2007) argued that in order to develop competence in an area of inquiry, people must observe/address the following:

- 1) Have a deep foundation of factual knowledge;
- 2) Understand facts and ideas in the context of a conceptual framework;
- 3) Organise knowledge in ways that facilitate retrieval and application.

This meant that a meta-cognitive approach to instruction could assist people to be in charge of their own learning by defining goals and then monitoring their progress toward achieving them.

It could be opined that the theoretical framework proposed by Timperley, Wilson, Barrar, and Fung (2007) above provided a powerful framework for thinking about how best to occasion teacher's learning and development. However, it is also important to acknowledge that factors critical to teachers education in some countries, such as the USA, may not hold the same significance in Nigeria. Therefore, frameworks developed for teachers' education in contexts like Malaysia, Turkey, or the UK may not be directly applicable to Nigeria. The relevance and success of different frameworks can vary significantly across countries, depending on the nuances of their legal, social, economic, financial, cultural, and political environments.

Recognizing this need for further research, scholars such as Conijn, Willeke, Evelien, Lucija, and Anders (2022), and Suib, Ghazali, Halim, Ariffin, and Razak (2022) have advocated for future investigations to deepen our understanding of teacher's education, particularly concerning improving teacher education in tertiary institutions in general. Accordingly, this paper is aimed at contributing to this body of knowledge by exploring the explanatory power of some theories in the extant literature with a view to achieving the purpose of this paper.

METHODOLOGY

This paper adopted a literature review and content analysis approach to explore the explanatory power of two interconnected theories – the Transformative Learning Theory (TLT) and the Human Capital Theory (HCT). The literature review method facilitated the collection of pertinent materials from diverse scholarly sources, including peer-reviewed journals, online policy documents and reports, conference proceedings, and library resources. These materials were then analyzed using content analysis.

This methodological combination is recognized as a robust strategy for synthesizing research findings at a meta-level, revealing broader patterns and highlighting areas requiring further investigation (Creswell, 2013). Such an approach is particularly well-suited for constructing theoretical and conceptual frameworks (Snyder, 2019). Systematic literature reviews, as employed here, are established research methods involving the identification and critical evaluation of relevant studies, alongside the systematic collection and analysis of data (Creswell, 2013).

Content analysis, in turn, involves the quantitative examination of text – often through keyword counts and comparative analysis – followed by a qualitative interpretation of the deeper contextual meanings embedded within the content (Hsieh & Shannon, 2014). Therefore, the integration of both literature review and content analysis provides a comprehensive and rigorous methodological framework for this study.

RESULTS/DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Theoretical Framework

There are many theory of education, and researchers have argued that a theoretical perspective is necessary in order to provide a comprehensive explanation on teacher education, or in explaining the antecedents of teacher's education for

performance improvement. However, this paper will benefit from the following two (2) theories: Transformative Learning Theory (TLT) and Human Capital Theory (HCT). Thus, in line with existing literature, this paper adopted two (2) independent but interrelated theories to serve as a framework of analysis. The two (2) theories are used to underpin and explain the relationships between the variables of the study. The choice of these theories was underscored by multiple causes and the explanation of inter-relationships by the theories. Thus, combining two or more theories serves to capitalise on their strengths and reduce their drawbacks, giving rise to a more robust theoretical underpinning as argued and suggested by Suib, Ghazali, Halim, Ariffin, and Razak (2022), and Suib, Ghazali, Halim, Ariffin, Razak (2022) who believed that using a two-theory approach can help provide a good understanding about teacher performance as a whole, by taking into consideration all of the key variables revealed in studies over the last five years.

Teacher education has become a common concept in education literature, yet its definition remains elusive and its use inconsistent especially within the context of primary, secondary and tertiary institutions. Due to its ambiguity, it becomes apparently difficult for researchers to adopt a single theory or approach in the explanations and analysis of the issues confronting teacher education in tertiary institutions in general.

On the other hand, Job performance is a diverse concept that is influenced by a variety of factors (Cohen, Hoz, & Kaplan 2013). Suib, Ghazali, Halim, Ariffin, Razak (2022) and König, Blömeke, and Kaiser (2017) revealed three (3) crucial gaps which included: unclear definition of teacher's performance, nature of participants (respondents), and the way one looks at job performance (i.e perspective). Suib et al (2022) specifically attributed two (2) pre-existing theories that have important bearing on teachers' performance. They are: 1) Social cognitive theory of organizational management, and 2) Leader member exchange theory or LMX. The theoretical framework was meant to provide better understanding of teacher performance by applying concepts from both theories. The theoretical framework implied that school leaders must provide conducive environmental along with personal or cognitive characteristics to teachers in order to improve their effectiveness.

Conversely, this study explored two (2) relevant theories to examine the relationship(s) between/among the constructs/variables of concern to this paper and developed a Theoretical and Conceptual framework. This was meant to improve teacher education in tertiary institutions in the study area (Gombe state). Detailed explanations of the theories are presented below:

Transformative Learning Theory (TLT)

Transformative Learning Theory (TLT) was propounded by Jack Mezirow in 1978. The theory was developed to describe learning with particular focus on adult education and young adult learning. One of the major assumptions of the TLT theory is that Transformative learning is sometimes called transformation learning, and focuses on the idea that learners can adjust their thinking based on new information. The theory is best illustrated by considering of a life- changing event. For instance the death of a spouse or situation of divorce. The experience of getting a first child, or becoming an 'employer'. Thus Mezirow is considered as th founder of transformative learning as he began this theory when he conducted studies on adult women who went back to school. Another assumption of this theory is that adults don't apply their old understanding to new situations; instead they find the need to look at new perspectives in order to get a new understanding of things as they change.

Mezirow theorized that students had important teaching and learning opportunities connected to their past experiences. He found that critical reflection and critical review could lead to a transformation of their understanding. Adult education and adult learning is key in this theory, as children often don't have the same kind of transformation with their learning experiences. Mezirow found that adult learning involves taking the very things we believed and thought as a child,

and letting critical reflection and teaching impact the transformation to what we should believe and understand now. Mezirow’s theory has developed into a larger idea that our world view is changed the more we learn, and that helps us grasp new concepts and ideas.

The fundamental tenets of the theory influenced adult education which generated enormous criticisms. of the TLT. For instance, Boyd and Myers argued that Mezirow’s theory was too rationalistic with its emphasis on deliberation and critical thinking as the primary driver of or that it focused too much on individual rather than social or collective transformation. Similarly, Cunningham (1992) and Inglis (1997) who were the postmodern critique against grand narratives of the TLT, arguing that Mezirow’s theory assumes a unified self, that self-direction and autonomy are universal values, and that a universal form of rationality exist. However, Mezirow debunked these and many other critiques, occasionally modifying his theory to reflect the issues that arose against the theory, while ignoring, or sometimes refusing to respond to the various criticisms. In addition to these exchanges, networks of TLT research and practice continued to flourish, which led to debates and conferences, including joint publications of other similar theories.

Human Capital Theory

The Human Capital Theory (HCT) was propounded by economists Gary Becker and Theodore Schultz in 1960. They stressed that education and training were important investments that has the potentials to increase productivity. The more the increase in physical capital, the more the more the opportunity cost of going to school decreased. The workforce requires qualified and competed people that are well educated.. The term was also adopted by corporate finance and became part of intellectual capital, and generally considered as human capital. Some of the assumptions of this theory are that intellectual and human capital is considered as renewable sources of productivity. This is because organizations endeavourer to inculcate a survival/sustainability culture with a view to add innovation or creativity. This is because, occasionally, a business problem requires more than just new machines or more money. There is a debate among economists about the influence of human capital on productivity; this implied several criticisms of the theory.

Harvard economist Richard Freeman have argued in 1976 that educations sector performance only acted as a signal about talent and ability; real productivity came later through training, motivation, and capital equipment. He concluded that education sector performance is not a factor of production. Similarly, Marxian economists Samuel Bowels and Herbert Gintis argued against the HCT, emphasizing that regarding people as capital undermines the argument that around class conflict and efforts to empower workers’ rights. This theory has established a vital relationship between teacher education and education sector performance. With teachers going back to school for further education, it gives them the opportunity to enhance their skills through labour productivity where they become for knowledgeable and competent to provide quality education to the students in their care. Hence, the theory was adopted for this study.

Table 1 shows the theories adopted for the paper, the assumptions of the theories and their application to the study.

Table 1: Theory, basic assumptions of the theory and application of the theory to the study

Theory	Transformative Learning Theory (TLT)	Human Capital Theory (HCT).
Proponents of the Theory	TLT was propounded by Jack Mezirow in 1978.	The HCT was propounded by Gary Becker and Theodore Schultz in 1960.
Basic Assumption(s) of the theory	1. Transformative learning is ALSO referred to as the transformation learning, and is based on the assumption that learners have the	1. They stressed that education and training were important investments that has the potentials to increase productivity. The more the increase

	<p>capacity to adjust their thinking in the light of new information.</p> <p>2. Another assumption of this theory is that adults fail to adopt their previous understanding of issues to new or changing circumstances; rather, they discover consider new perspectives so as to obtain proper understanding of issues a they evolve.</p>	<p>in physical capital, the more the more the opportunity cost of going to school decreased. Investments in education and training has the potentials to positively influence productivity. As the world accumulated more and more physical capital, the opportunity cost of going to school declined. Education continued to be a crucial component of the workforce.</p> <p>2. Intellectual and human capital are considered as a sustainable source of productivity. This is because organizations try to cultivate these sources, hoping for added innovation or creativity.</p>
<p>Application of theory to the study</p>	<p>Mezirow theorized that past experiences provided important opportunities for students in terms of teaching and learning.</p> <p>In addition, Mezirow revealed that critical reflection and critical review has the capacity to influence student understanding of issues.</p> <p>Furthermore, adult education and adult learning are very important in this theory, because children often do not have similar transformation with their learning experiences. Hence, the adoption/application of the theory to this study.</p>	<p>Human Capital Theory (HCT). has established a vital relationship between teacher education and education sector performance. With teachers going back to school for further education, it gives them the opportunity to enhance their skills through labour productivity where they become far knowledgeable and competent to provide quality education to the students in their care. Hence, the adoption/application of the theory to this study</p>

CONCLUSION

In this paper, a theoretical and conceptual framework is presented designed to illuminate the main concepts/variables of concern to the paper and their relationship. This was accomplished through a rigorous literature review and content analysis, exploring the explanatory power of two interconnected theoretical lenses: Transformative Learning and the Human Capital Theories.

Drawing upon the Transformative Learning Theory (TLT), we posited that students had important teaching and learning opportunities connected to their past experiences. It was found that critical reflection and critical review could lead to a transformation of their understanding. Adult education and adult learning is key in this theory, as children often don't have the same kind of transformation with their learning experiences. The TLT posits that adult learning involves taking the very things we believed and thought as a child, and letting critical reflection and teaching impact the transformation to what we should believe and understand now (Suib, Ghazali, Halim, Ariffin, & Razak, 2022). The theory has developed into a larger idea that our world view is changed the more we learn, and that helps us grasp new concepts and ideas which can potentially overcome the limitations and a lack of extensive experience – challenges often faced by teachers in tertiary educational institutions. This could be achieved through strategic learning and robust interactions with other stakeholders / players in the educational sector. This rationale led us to explore the Human Capital Theory (HCT) as a means to address the inherent

limitations of the Transformative Learning Theory (TLT) perspective in this context. Therefore, this paper turned to the Human Capital Theory (HCT) theory to further explain the potential pathways for improving teachers' education, recognizing that robust learning and experience are significantly strengthened with human Capital development. The Human Capital Theory (HCT) theory offers the insight that while learning and experience can present constraints, they can also become assets if tertiary institutions develop the adaptive capacity to navigate and leverage them effectively with the help of human Capital development (Conijn, Willeke, Evelien, Lucija, & Anders, 2022).

In the context of this study, the Human Capital Theory (HCT) has established a vital relationship between teacher education and education sector performance. With teachers going back to school for further education, it gives them the opportunity to enhance their skills through labour productivity where they become knowledgeable and competent to provide quality education to the students in their care. This suggests that tertiary institutions in the study area stand to benefit from existing policies and programmes of the Federal Ministry of Education (FME) provided they cultivate organizational agility and adaptability.

This paper offers notable implications for both theory and practice. Theoretically, it provides a foundational framework for understanding teacher education through the combined lens of the Transformative Learning Theory (TLT) and the Human Capital Theory (HCT) theory. Practically, it serves as a call to action. It underscores the need for government support in formulating policies that encourage and facilitate the improvement of teachers' education, and it aims to positively influence heads of tertiary education institutions in the study area to strategically consider improvement in their school curriculum.

The paper has some limitations being that it is not exhaustive. This suggests the need for further research in view of the scarcity/paucity of research on teachers education particularly in the study area thus, contributing to teacher education discuss.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the foregoing, the paper proffered the following recommendations:

1. Future research should explicitly consider the explanatory powers of these two (2) relevant but inter-related theories: the Transformative Learning Theory (TLT) and the Human Capital Theory (HCT) theories as integral and relevant lenses for achieving improvement and success in teachers' education in tertiary institutions in general.
2. The federal government should provide support towards policy formulation on teacher education in particular, with a view to positively influence heads of tertiary institutions to consider a review of their curriculum and approach to teaching and provision of facilities in view of the benefits.

REFERENCES

- Abduljabbar, O. A. (2022). Teacher Education and National Development: The Nigerian Experience. *Zamfara Journal of Politics and Development*, 3(3), 12-27.
- Abdullahi, R. (2024). Gombe State Education Sector Development and the Ills of Malpractices. *RISW*, 5(1), 555-789.
- Adamu, A., (2024). Teacher education and the performance of tertiary institutions in Gombe state, Nigeria. Unpublished thesis, (Senior Executive Course 46, 2024) National Institute for Policy and Strategic studies (NIPSS) Kuru, Plateau state, Nigeria.
- Adamu, B. (2021). Perception of teachers on motivational factors improving teaching profession in Gombe Local Government Area of Gombe, state. [Perception of Public Primary School Teachers on Motivational Factors improving Teaching Profession in Gombe Local Government Area of Gombe State \(researchgate.net\)](https://www.researchgate.net/publication/358123456)

- Adamu, B. (2023). Assessment of teachers' practices on student's learning process in senior secondary schools in Gombe Local Gombe Area. *Journal of Education*, 10(1), 79-89.
- Adesina, O., Yomi, W. & Aliyu, B. (2023). "Nigerian and the Challenges Education for Economic Development, *Development Journal*, 3(2): 34-67.
- Aglazor, G. (2017). The role of teaching practice in teacher education programmes: Designing framework for best practice. *Global Journal of Educational Research*, 16, 101-110. <https://doi.org/10.4314/gjedr.v16i2.4>
- Andric, A. (2023). Sweden – National Digitalisation Strategy for the School System 2023-2027.
- Arora, G. L. (2002). *Teachers and Their Teaching* Delhi, Ravi Books.
- Avgitidou, S., & Sidiropoulou, C. H. (2020). Deconstructing and reconstructing the beliefs of candidate teachers: An intervention programme in the framework of teaching practice. *Research in Education*, 9(1), 77-91. <https://doi.org/10.12681/hjre.23311>
- Bashari, H., Usman, W. & Kala, R. (2023). Social Development and Teacher Education in Gombe State. *Journal of Education and Science*, 4(2), 56-90.
- Bebeji, A. (2023). Education and the Challenges of Poverty in Gombe State. *Journal of Education Development*, 6(2), 345-678.
- Conijn, J., Rietdijk, W., Broekhof, E., Andre, L., & Schinkel, A. (2022). A theoretical framework and questionnaire for wonder-full education. *Journal of Curriculum Studies*, 54(3), 423-444. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00220272.2021.1942992>
- Cohen, E., Hoz, R., & Kaplan, H. (2013). The practicum in pre-service teacher education: A review of empirical studies. *Teaching Education*, 24(4), 345-380. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10476210.2012.711815>
- Creswell, J. W. (2013). *Research design: Qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods*. (4th ed.). Thousand Oaks, London: Sage Publication.
- Federal Ministry of Budget (2024). National Development Plan 2021-2025. www.fmb.ng/ndp-2021-2025.er.v/2
- Federal Ministry of Education (2024). National Policy on Education 2014. national-education-policy-2013.pdf (wordpress.com)
- Federal Ministry of Education (2024). National Policy on ICT Education 2019. NATIONAL-POLICY-ON-ICT-IN-EDUCATION-2019.pdf
- Gombe State Ministry of Education (2024). About Gombe State Ministry of Education. [MOE \(gm.gov.ng\)](http://MOE(gm.gov.ng))
- Gombe State Ministry of Finance (2024). Gombe State Strategic Development Plan 2021-2030. [Budget Office Policies and Reports - Ministry of Finance, Gombe state \(gm.gov.ng\)](http://Budget Office Policies and Reports - Ministry of Finance, Gombe state (gm.gov.ng))
- Gombe State UBEC (2024). About Gombe State UBEC. [Gombe – Universal Basic Education Commission \(UBEC\)](http://Gombe – Universal Basic Education Commission (UBEC)).
- Hsieh, H., & Shannon, S. E. (2014). Three Approaches to Qualitative Content Analysis. *Research Gate*: Retrieved from <https://www.researchgate.net7>
- Jaafar, M., Ubale, I. & Maigari, R. (2023). The Challenges of Education and Diversity in Gombe State. *Education and Science*, 2(1), 23-78.
- Kampeza, M. (2013). Factors students consider important in the evaluation of their teaching practice. In A. Androusou, & S. Avgitidou (Eds.), *Teaching practice in initial teacher training: Research approaches* (pp. 197-224). Athens: Teaching Practice Network, Department of Early Childhood Education, NKUA.

- Kuroshi, P. (2014). Construction practices and skills gap in the construction industry. Registrar, Council of Registered Builders of Nigeria (CORBON). 2nd Floor Kays Plaza, Obafemi Awolowo way, Jabi – Abuja.
- Odusanmi, K. T. & Unoma, G. E. (2011). Tackling the Shortage of Construction Skills in Nigeria. Paper Presented at a 2-Day National Seminar Organised by the Nigerian Institute of Quantity Surveyors, Vision 20-2020: Strategic Industry Development within National Development Goals.
- National Commission for Colleges of Education (2024). About NCCE. [Welcome Home - NCCE Abuja](#)
- Ndebele, C., Morongwe, N., Ncanywa, T., Matope, S., Ginyigazi, Z., Chisango, G., Nsidwana, P. N. & Garidzirai, R. (2024). Reconceptualising Initial Teacher Education in South Africa: A Quest for Transformative and Sustainable Alternatives. *Interdisciplinary Journal of Education research*, (6) 1-19.
- Nordin, M. A., Noor, M. A., Mutalib, N. N., & Sidek, A. (2021). Teacher Education in Malaysia. *Turkish Journal of Physiotherapy and Rehabilitation*; 32(3), 4810-416.
- Oluwatosin, A. M. & Bolanle, A. F. (2024). Teachers' education in Nigeria: Challenges and the Way Forward. *An International Scientific Journal*, 1(88), 67-80.
- Osokoya, I. (2022). Teacher Education in Nigeria: Past, Present and Future Challenges. *Academical Online Leadership Journal*, 8(4), 1-9.
- Oviawe, J. I., Imhangbe, O. S., Aluede, O., Obinya, G. & Oke, T. D. (2022). Challenges and Emerging Perspectives of Quality Assurance and Teacher Education in Nigerian Universities: A Literature Review. [Challenges and Emerging Perspectives of Quality Assurance and Teacher Education in Nigerian Universities: A Literature Review \(degruyter.com\)](#)
- Oyekan, S. O. (2000). Foundations of teacher education Okitipupa: Ebun-Ola printers Nig. Ltd.
- Ramalan, G., Rashida, T. & Lawali, R. (2023). Gombe State Education Sector and the Challenges of Economic Development, *GOMS*, 4(2), 45-67.
- Rashid, A. (2024). Education and National Development in Nigeria: Gombe State Study. Unpublished Masters of Science in Education thesis, Gombe State University.
- Rob, A. (2020). Understanding Performance. [Understanding Performance \(tutorialspoint.com\)](#)
- Rodrick, F. (2020). Education Performance. *Science and Education*, 3(4), 23-56.
- Snyder, H. (2019). Literature review as a research methodology: An overview and guidelines. *Journal of Business Research*, (104), 333–339. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2019.07.039>
- Timperley, H., Wilson, A., Barrar, H., & Fung, I. (2007). Teacher professional learning and development: Best evidence synthesis iteration [BES]. New Zealand Ministry of Education.
- United Nations Education, Scientific and Cultural Organisation (2023) “Teachers and Educational Quality” [teachers-and-educational-quality-monitoring-global-needs-for-2015-en_0.pdf \(unesco.org\)](#)
- Universal Basic Education Commission (2024). About UBEC. [About Us – Universal Basic Education Commission \(UBEC\)](#)
- World Bank (2023). Gombe State Better Education Service Delivery for All. www.worldbankgroup.com
- World Bank (2024). Global Education Performance Review. [Education Overview: Development news, research, data | World Bank](#)